

Investigation of 30% rule for the combination of component response with the unidirectional principal response spectrum

P.B. Kote¹, S.N. Madhekar², and I. D. Gupta³

¹ Research Scholar, Department of Civil Engineering, College of Engineering Pune, Pune 411 005.

² Professor, Department of Civil Engineering, College of Engineering Pune, Pune 411 005.

and

³ Director (Former), C.W.P.R.S, Pune 411 024.

Presenting Author: P.B. Kote, Email: pkotenetwork@gmail.com

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Abstract

The paper investigates the validity of the [Max +30%] rule by comparing the results for a typical six-story steel building with the exact results based on the response spectrum in the principal direction and, the critical response spectrum providing an upper bound to multi-directional component response. Three different sets of real earthquake ground motions with widely differing characteristics are used. It has been found that the [Max + 30%] rule, which is included in IS 1893 (2016) may not lead to realistic results in all the cases.

Keywords: Response Spectrum analysis; Principal directional response spectrum; IS 1893 (2016); CSI SAP2000.

1 Introduction

The ground motion caused by an earthquake can be considered as the resultant of three orthogonal translation components along three Cartesian coordinates x , y , and z ; and three rotational components about these three co-ordinate axes.

Many investigators have recognized the necessity of finding the response of structures under multi-component earthquake excitation. Bolotin [1] presented a stochastic theory of structural response to multi-component seismic loading. Penzien and Watabe [2] pointed out the importance of finding the response caused by three translational components of earthquake motion and studied the characteristics of three-dimensional ground motion.

Chen [3] investigated the statistical dependence of the three components of ground motion. Gelman worked on the combination of the translational component sine of the horizontal direction. Rosenblueth and Contreras [4] developed an approximate procedure for combining the response component. They expressed the resultant response as a linear combination of the components of interest and found the coefficient of expansion so that the error is minimized. Wilson and Button [5] presented a method for three-dimensional dynamic analysis for multi-component earthquake spectra.

Other works suggest the methods of combining the maxima of the three components of response, where each of the component's maxima is found by the customary modal superposition methods using response spectra of the corresponding ground acceleration component. Chu, Amin, and Singh [6] suggested the square root of the sum of the squares (SRSS) method for finding the resultant of three partial responses. The USNRC [7] recommended this method for combining three special responses. The

[Max+30%] method suggested by Resenblueth and Contreras [4] is recommended by ATC-3(1978) provisions. In this method; the resultant is taken as the maximum component under consideration plus 30% of the sum of all other components.

Anagnostopoulos [8] made a comparative study of different modal and spatial combination method. In addition to SRSS and [Max+30%] rule, he compared the methods, viz SUM, SRLS and their averages with SRSS. He also used the [Max+40%] and [Max+50%] components, whereas in NRLS method resultant is defined as the maximum of three component plus the SRSS of the other two. This was suggested as a modal superposition method by O'Hara and Cunfit [9].

Though it is well recognized that the response of important structures like nuclear reactor components, dams, and long-span bridges, may be dependent on all the three translational components of motion, due to complexity of the three dimensional analysis and various uncertainty in spatial combination procedures, most of the studies considered only one component of earthquake motion. Hadjian [10] showed that the common spatial combination rules like SRSS and [Max+30%] have been derived on the assumption of statistical independence between components of the response, though such assumption may not be always justified. Anagnostopoulos [8] showed that because of the correlation between components of earthquake motion, additive response effects are created in corner members of the three-dimensional structure. Moreover, all the above-mentioned spatial combination rules combine the maxima of the component's responses to get the maximum of the resultant, whereas the component maxima do not occur at the same time.

Haluk et al [11], considered spectrum intensity concept to investigate the bi-directional effects of earthquakes and the

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effectiveness of spectrum intensity method. In the study vertical component of the ground motion was excluded, assuming that the horizontal components are the governing components for a building analysis. However, the vertical component can be included in a similar way, when the principal component is in the vertical direction.

In the present work, the authors have investigated the validity of the [Max+30%] rule by comparing the results for a typical 6 story steel building shown in Figure 1, with the exact results based on the response spectrum in the principal direction and the critical response spectrum, providing an upper bound to multi-directional component response using three different real earthquakes with widely differing characteristics. It has been found that the [Max+30%] rule may not always lead to realistic results.

2 Particulars of the building

A typical six-story steel moment resisting frame building is considered with 4 bays in the x -direction and 3 bays in the y -direction, as shown in Figure 1. The building is analysed for dead load and appropriate imposed load as specified in IS 1893(2016). The damping ratio considered is 5%. The time periods (s) for the steel building for the first 9 modes of vibration are 1.319, 1.247, 1.215, 0.409, 0.405, 0.378, 0.246, 0.218, 0.216 respectively and the natural frequencies (rad/s) for the first 9 modes of vibration are 4.762, 5.039, 5.173, 15.363, 15.510, 16.613, 25.505, 28.786, 29.103, respectively.

3 Input Excitation

To perform the numerical study, response spectra of the three real earthquake records are used. The details of the considered earthquakes are given in Table 1.

To compute the response by commonly used [Max+30%] rule, geometric mean of the response spectra [SAGM] in two horizontal components has been used. To compare these results, it is proposed to use two different spectra; spectrum in the major principal direction [SAXP] and the critical spectrum [SACRIT]. The SAXP is obtained by resolving the components of the original accelerogram record in the major principal direction and SACRIT is obtained by the resultant response of an SDOF system at each natural period of vibration.

The spectra for the three selected earthquake records are shown in Figure 2. Table 2 gives the spectral amplitudes at the fundamental frequency of the steel moment resisting frame building in x and y -direction.

Figure 1. Typical 6 Story Steel Building

Table 1. Details of the selected earthquakes

EQ#	Name of EQ	Date	M	Focal Depth [km]	Epicenter distance [km]	PGA [g]	Recording station
1	Gorkha Nepal	25/04/2015	7.9	13.4	13.6	0.754	Kirtipur
2	Sikkim	18/09/2011	6.7	10.00	50.3	0.569	Gangtok
3	Uttarkas hi	20/10/1991	6.9	13.2	73.9	1.083	Bhatwari

Table 2. Spectral Amplitudes at Fundamental Period of Building in x and y direction

REC #	SAGM [m/s ²]		SAXP [m/s ²]		SACRIT [m/s ²]	
	x	y	x	y	x	y
1	1.17	1.15	1.58	1.53	1.60	1.56
2	0.27	0.24	0.35	0.31	0.35	0.31
3	2.31	2.03	3.68	3.27	3.74	3.36

(2a) Response spectrum of Nepal Earthquake

(2b) Response spectrum of Sikkim Earthquake

(2c) Response spectrum of Uttarkashi Earthquake
Figure 2. Earthquake Response Spectra

4 Numerical Analysis and Results

SAGM has been used to compute the maximum displacement and story shear in both x and y directions of the building using CQC modal combination rules and the resultant response is obtained as follows

$$x_R = x_{max} + 0.3 y_{max} \quad (1)$$

In Equation (1), x_{max} and y_{max} are the maximum responses in x and y directions and x_R is the resultant response in x direction.

The SAXP spectrum is proposed to get a realistic estimate of resultant response in x or y direction, simply by unidirectional analysis. Use of SACRIT is proposed to get upper bound in resultant response in x or y direction. Dynamic analysis is performed with the help of CSI SAP2000 V20.

The resultant response of the steel building in x -direction computed using Equation (1) is presented in Figure 3, which compares the resultant response based on the conventional 30% rule with the resultant response based on the only unidirectional analysis using the principal and critical response spectra.

(3a) Story Displacement for Nepal RS

(3b) Story Displacement for Sikkim RS

(3c) Story Displacement for Uttarkashi RS
Figure 3. Story Displacement

Similarly, story shear is calculated. The story shear distribution plot is obtained as given in Figure 4.

(4a) Base Shear for Nepal RS

(4b) Base Shear for Sikkim RS

(4c) Base Shear for Sikkim RS

Figure 4. Base Shear Distribution

It is seen that for Uttarkashi Earthquake spectra the response obtained by [Max+30%] rule is much lesser than that obtained in principal direction response spectrum and Critical response spectra. Thus 30% rule may not be adequate in all cases. As expected; results obtained for critical response spectra are even higher than the principal direction spectrum.

5 Conclusions

For Uttarkashi earthquake, depending upon the characteristics of earthquake ground motion, results obtained from [Max+30%] rule response are less than the expected results. Hence [Max+30%] rule may not work equally well in all cases and it may lead to higher or lower estimates compared with the desired estimate in the principal direction. However, in no case, the 30% combination rule exceeds the estimate based on critical response spectrum. The following conclusions are drawn based on the numerical investigation.

- Estimation of the response of the multidirectional excitation can be performed in a much simpler and efficient way, using unidirectional principal response spectrum analysis.
- Ground Motion Prediction Equations (GMPE) must be developed for the principal as well as the critical response spectrum.

6 References

- Bolotin, V. V. Structural Response of the Multi-component Seismic Loading considered as a Non-Stationary Random Process. *Proc. of the first Chilean session on Seismology and Earthquake Engineering*. 1963; Santiago.
- Penzien J and Watae M. Characteristics of three-dimensional earthquake ground motion. *Journal of Earthquake Engineering and structural dynamics*. 1975; **3**:365-373.
- Chen C. Definition of Statistically Independent Time Histories. *Journal of Structural Division ASCE*. 1975; **101**:449-451.
- Rosenblueth E and Contreras H. Approximate Design for Multi-Component Earthquake *Journal of Engineering Mechanics Division, ASCE*. 1977; **103**:881-893.
- Wilson E. L. and Butten M.R. Three-Dimensional dynamic analysis for multi-component Earthquake Spectra', *Earthquake Engineering and Structural Dynamics*. 1982; **10**:471-479.
- Chu S.L., Amin. M. and Singh S. Special treatment of actions of three earthquakes components on structures. *Nuclear Engineering and Design*. 1972; **21**:126-316.
- U.S. Nuclear Regulatory Commission. Combining Modal Responses and Spatial components in Seismic Response Analysis. *Regulatory Guide 192, Revision-1*. 1973; Washington D. C.
- Anagnostopoulos S.A., Response Spectrum Techniques for Three Component Earthquake Design. *Journal of Earthquake Engineering and structural dynamics*. 1981; **9**:459-476.
- O'Hara G.J. and Cunniff P.F. Elements of Normal Mode Theory- NRL Report 6002, *U.S. Naval Research Laboratory*. 1953; Washington D.C.
- Hadjian A.H. On the Correlation of the components of strong ground motion. *Proc 2nd International Conference on Micro-zonation San Francisco*. 1978; **3**:1199-1120.
- Haluk S. Oguz C.C., Feridun C. Review and evaluation of combination rules for structures under bi-directional earthquake excitations. *13th World Conference on Earthquake Engineering*. 2004; **2079**.
- Gupta I. D. and M. D. Trifunac, Order Statistics of Peaks of the Response to multi-component seismic excitation. *Bull. Ind. Soc. Earthquake Tech.*, 1987; **258, 24**:135-259.